

GENERAL EXACT SOLUTIONS FOR THE MODE SHAPES OF LONGITUDINALLY VIBRATING NON-UNIFORM RODS VIA LIE SYMMETRIES

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Abstract. A Lie symmetry method-based approach is proposed for systematically computing general solutions in closed-form for the mode shape equation of non-uniform and unconventional vibrating rods from the elementary rod theory, addressing polynomial, exponential, trigonometric, and hyperbolic cross-section variations. The method provides algorithmic order-reduction steps for the investigated mode shape equation, producing a first-order Riccati equation whose integration originates the aimed general solutions for the problem. Illustrative examples bring original solutions, recover several literature cases, and derive mode shapes with appropriate boundary conditions for rods.

Keywords: general solutions, non-uniform rods, elementary rod theory, mode shapes, Lie symmetries.

1. INTRODUCTION

The study of structural elements undergoing longitudinal vibration is crucial for several scientific and industrial applications' design, safety, and efficiency (Santo *et al.*, 2020; Zhu and Li, 2017). Rod models comprise the longitudinal motion of thin elastic structures under many loads, geometry configurations, and frequency ranges, whose response predictions usually derive from their modal properties, i.e., mode shapes, modal frequencies, and modal damping (Kinsler *et al.*, 1999; Love, 2013; Mindlin and Herrmann, 1989; Viktorov, 2013). Despite the practicality of numerical methods for solving such models, remarkable benefits arise from exact solutions, e.g., avoiding studies of convergence, concerning about cumulative errors, and reducing computational time (Ardourel and Jebeile, 2016). Few exact solutions are available in the literature for the mode shapes of non-uniform rods once the complexity of the associated differential equations (DEs) makes it difficult for their computation. When existing, these solutions occur from apparently unconnected ad hoc methods for solving DEs (Kumar and Sujith, 1997; Yardimoglu and Aydin, 2011; Guo and Yang, 2011). The Lie symmetry method reveals potential transformations for constructing exact solutions for DEs, unifying and extending many integration techniques for DEs through a systematic algorithm based on the existence of Lie symmetry groups (Olver, 1986). This paper presents the procedure for computing general solutions via the Lie symmetry method for the mode shape equation of longitudinally vibrating non-uniform rods, modeled according to the elementary rod theory. From that, a systematic and elegant way of deriving general solutions arises from recalling previous literature cases and addressing new non-uniform configurations, which establishes mode shapes together with the boundary conditions of the rod.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the equivalent mode shape equation and its mathematical correspondence for rods with varying cross-section areas and completely non-uniform geometrical and material distributions. In addition, it introduces the Lie symmetry method for ordinary differential equations (ODEs). Section 3 provides the equivalent mode shape equation rods with an order reduction via the Lie symmetry method and establishes a systematic procedure for computing its general solutions in closed form. This section also considers an example for deriving mode shapes from its general solutions, illustrating the interchangeability of solutions between completely non-uniform and simply varying cross-section area rods. Finally, Section 4 brings the concluding remarks.

2. METHODOLOGY

This section derives an equivalent equation to the mode shape equation for non-uniform rods and introduces the Lie symmetry method for ODEs. The reader is referred to Bluman and Anco (2002); Olver (1986); Cantwell (2002); Ovsiannikov (1982) for a comprehensive description of symmetry methods.

2.1 Equivalent mode shape equation for non-uniform rods

The elastodynamic equation from the elementary model for rods with non-uniform cross-sections undergoing free longitudinal vibrating follows as (Inman, 2013):

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(E S \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \tilde{u}(x, t) \right) - \rho S \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \tilde{u}(x, t) = 0, \quad x \in]l_1, l_2[, \quad t > 0, \quad (1)$$

where $\tilde{u}(x, t)$ is the rod's time-dependent longitudinal displacement, x represents the position along the structure, and t denotes time, whereas $E = E(x)$ is the Young's modulus, $S = S(x)$ is the cross-section area function and $\rho = \rho(x)$ is the density of the rod. By introducing the variable $y = \int_0^x [E_0 \rho(\tau) / (E(\tau) \rho_0)]^{\frac{1}{2}} d\tau$, the combined use of the chain rule and the inverse function theorem leads to (Guo and Yang, 2011; Zhong and Nie, 1997):

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(E_0 \bar{S} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \tilde{u}(y, t) \right) - \rho_0 \bar{S} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \tilde{u}(y, t) = 0, \quad (2)$$

for E_0 and ρ_0 being the Young's modulus and the density of the rod at its cross-section labeled as the origin, respectively, and $\bar{S} = [E \rho / (E_0 \rho_0)]^{\frac{1}{2}} S$. Let $\tilde{u} = u e^{j\omega t}$ be a harmonic non-trivial solution, where $u = u(y)$ and ω represent the general solution for the mode shape functions and the natural angular frequencies of the rod, respectively, and j be the imaginary unit. From this, Eq. (2) can be written equivalently to the mode shape equation as follows:

$$\frac{1}{\bar{S}} \frac{d}{dy} \left(\bar{S} \frac{du}{dy} \right) + \lambda_0^2 u = 0, \quad (3)$$

where $\lambda_0 = (\rho_0 / E_0)^{\frac{1}{2}} \omega$ is the *quasi*-longitudinal wavenumber at the origin (Frank J. Fahy, 2006).

2.2 Lie symmetries of a given ODE

In general terms, a Lie symmetry group addresses transformations that maps solutions of DEs into other solutions. The knowledge of a Lie symmetry group for a given DE or system of DEs leads to coordinate changes that retain the equations' solutions invariant. These invariants may produce analytical order reductions, linearizations, and domain compressions for directly constructing exact solutions. Such procedure is highly algorithmic and is given for ODEs as follows. Consider an N th-order ODE written in the form:

$$\mathcal{F}(y, u, u_1, \dots, u_N) = 0, \quad (4)$$

where u and y denote the dependent and independent variables, respectively, and $u_k = d^k u / dy^k$, for $k = 1, \dots, N$. Let \mathcal{X} represent a smooth vector field defined on the space of coordinates (y, u) as the infinitesimal generator (Olver, 1986):

$$\mathcal{X} = \xi \frac{\partial}{\partial y} + \eta \frac{\partial}{\partial u}, \quad (5)$$

where the functions $\xi = \xi(y, u)$ and $\eta = \eta(y, u)$ are called the infinitesimals of \mathcal{X} . Such vector field can be prolonged to the space with coordinates (y, u, u_1, \dots, u_N) in which Eq. (4) is defined by (Hydon, 2000; Cantwell, 2002):

$$\mathcal{X}^{(N)} = \mathcal{X} + \eta^{(1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial u_1} + \dots + \eta^{(N)} \frac{\partial}{\partial u_N}, \quad \text{for } \eta^{(0)} = \eta, \quad \eta^{(i)} = \mathcal{D}(\eta^{(i-1)}) - u_i \mathcal{D}(\xi), \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \quad (6)$$

and the total derivative operator is $\mathcal{D} = \partial / \partial y + u_1 \partial / \partial u + u_2 \partial / \partial u_1 + \dots$.

The infinitesimal criterion of invariance checks if the flow of the vector fields provides admitted Lie symmetry groups for Eq. (4), which requires (Bluman and Anco, 2002):

$$\mathcal{X}^{(N)} \mathcal{F}(y, u, u_1, \dots, u_N) = 0 \quad \text{when} \quad \mathcal{F}(y, u, u_1, \dots, u_N) = 0, \quad (7)$$

and is parsed into a system of linear partial differential equations for ξ and η by equating the derivative's coefficients to zero with $u_N = f(y, u, u_1, \dots, u_{N-1})$ from Eq. (4), known as the system of determining equations Baumann (2000).

Each element of the Lie symmetry group of a given ODE provides new functionally independent coordinates as follows:

$$\mathcal{X} r = 0, \quad \mathcal{X}^{(1)} v = 0, \quad (8)$$

for $r = r(y, u)$ and $v = v(y, u, u_1)$ as the integration constants of $dy/d\xi = du/d\eta = du_1/d\eta^{(1)}$, and by derivation:

$$v_k = \frac{\mathcal{D} v_{k-1}}{\mathcal{D} r}. \quad (9)$$

The set $\{r, v, v_1, \dots, v_{N-1}\}$ yields a reduced equation of the form (Bluman, 1990):

$$\mathcal{G}(r, v, v_1, \dots, v_{N-1}) = 0, \quad (10)$$

thus, assuming that $v = G(r; \mathcal{C}_1, \dots, \mathcal{C}_{N-1})$ represents its solution and \mathcal{C}_i are the integration constants, the general solution of Eq. (4) can be reconstructed through the auxiliary first-order equation:

$$v(y, u, u_1) = G(r(y, u); \mathcal{C}_1, \dots, \mathcal{C}_{N-1}), \quad (11)$$

whose integration recovers u through a systematic procedure since it inherits \mathcal{X} as a Lie symmetry transformation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Let Eq. (6) be the prolonged infinitesimals, the Lie point transformations, of the mode shape equation from Eq. (3). From Eq. (7):

$$\mathcal{X}^{(2)} \left(u_2 + \frac{1}{\bar{S}} \frac{d\bar{S}}{dy} u_1 + \lambda_0^2 u \right) = 0, \quad \text{when } u_2 + \frac{1}{\bar{S}} \frac{d\bar{S}}{dy} u_1 + \lambda_0^2 u = 0, \quad (12)$$

whose evaluation yields the system of determining equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial u^2} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial y^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial y \partial u} - \frac{1}{\bar{S}} \frac{d\bar{S}}{dy} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial y} - 3 \lambda_0^2 u \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial u} - \left[\frac{d^2 \bar{S}}{dy^2} - \frac{1}{\bar{S}} \left(\frac{d\bar{S}}{dy} \right)^2 \right] \frac{\xi}{\bar{S}} = 0, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial u^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial y \partial u} + 2 \frac{1}{\bar{S}} \frac{d\bar{S}}{dy} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial u} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial y^2} + \lambda_0^2 u \left(2 \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial u} \right) + \frac{1}{\bar{S}} \frac{d\bar{S}}{dy} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial y} + \lambda_0^2 \eta = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The pair $\xi = 0$ and $\eta = u$ is an admitted solution for the system and associated with $\mathcal{X}_1 = u \partial / \partial u$. Within such Lie point transformation, the invariance relations from Eq. (8) and Eq. (9) produce the differential invariants:

$$r = y, \quad v = \frac{u_1}{u}, \quad v_1 = \frac{u_2}{u} - \left(\frac{u_1}{u} \right)^2. \quad (14)$$

providing Eq. (3) with a change of variables in such a way that this ODE is transformed into the Riccati equation:

$$v_1 + \frac{1}{\bar{S}} \frac{d\bar{S}}{dr} v + v^2 + \lambda_0^2 = 0, \quad (15)$$

for $v = v(r)$ and $\bar{S} = \bar{S}(r)$ in the new space of the coordinates (r, v, v_1) .

The solution $v = v(r; \mathcal{C}_1)$ of Eq. (15) for specific cross-section variations allows to recover general solutions for Eq. (3) in closed form through the auxiliary first-order Eq. (11) resolution:

$$u = \mathcal{C}_2 e^{\int v(y; \mathcal{C}_1) dy}, \quad (16)$$

being \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 integration constants.

3.1 Example: mode shapes of a clamped-clamped rod with the cross-section area $S = a_1 a_2^{a_3 x}$

Consider a rod with a homogeneous material distribution $E = E_0$ and $\rho = \rho_0$ and the cross-section area $S = a_1 a_2^{a_3 x}$ for $a_1, a_2, a_3 \in \mathbb{R}$ and $a_2 > 0$. In this case, Eq. (15) assumes the form:

$$v_1 + v^2 + \ln(a_2) a_3 v + \lambda_0^2 = 0, \quad (17)$$

for $y = x$ and $\bar{S} = S$, whose resolution reduces to the computation of the primitive $-\int dv / (v^2 + \ln(a_2) a_3 v + \lambda_0^2)$, since it is a separable equation. The following three cases are distinguished:

$$v(r) = -\mu_1 \tan[\mu_1 (\mathcal{C}_1 + r)] - \frac{\ln(a_2) a_3}{2}, \quad 4\lambda_0^2 > \ln^2(a_2) a_3^2, \quad (18)$$

$$v(r) = \mu_2 \tanh[\mu_2 (\mathcal{C}_1 + r)] - \frac{\ln(a_2) a_3}{2}, \quad 4\lambda_0^2 < \ln^2(a_2) a_3^2, \quad (19)$$

and

$$v(r) = \frac{1}{(\mathcal{C}_1 + r)} - \frac{\ln(a_2) a_3}{2}, \quad 4\lambda_0^2 = \ln^2(a_2) a_3^2, \quad (20)$$

for $\mu_1 = (4\lambda_0^2 - \ln^2(a_2) a_3^2)^{1/2} / 2$ and $\mu_2 = (\ln^2(a_2) a_3^2 - 4\lambda_0^2)^{1/2} / 2$.

According to Eq. (16), the general solution for each subcase follows as:

$$u(x) = \mathcal{C}_2 a_2^{-\frac{a_3}{2}(\mathcal{C}_1+x)} \cos[\mu_1 (\mathcal{C}_1 + x)], \quad 4\lambda_0^2 > \ln^2(a_2) a_3^2, \quad (21)$$

$$u(x) = \mathcal{C}_2 a_2^{-\frac{a_3}{2}(\mathcal{C}_1+x)} \cosh[\mu_2 (\mathcal{C}_1 + x)], \quad 4\lambda_0^2 < \ln^2(a_2) a_3^2, \quad (22)$$

and

$$u(x) = \mathcal{C}_2 a_2^{-\frac{a_3}{2}x} (\mathcal{C}_1 + x), \quad 4\lambda_0^2 = \ln^2(a_2) a_3^2. \quad (23)$$

A clamped-clamped rod admits the boundary conditions $u(0) = u(l) = 0$ for $x \in [0, l]$. Assuming the frequency range where $4\lambda_0^2 > a_3^2$ and $a_2 = e$ alike in Guo and Yang (2011)'s case, the constants are $\mathcal{C}_1 = \pi / (4\lambda_0^2 - a_3^2)^{1/2}$ and \mathcal{C}_2 arbitrary. From that, the characteristic frequency equation is $\sin[(4\lambda_0^2 - a_3^2)^{1/2} l / 2] = 0$, that yields the roots $\lambda_{0(1)} = 3.18 \text{ m}^{-1}$ and $\lambda_{0(10)} = 31.41 \text{ m}^{-1}$ for the first and tenth wavenumbers, respectively, when considering the geometric parameters $a_1 = 1 \text{ m}$, $a_3 = 1 \text{ m}^{-1}$, and $l = 1 \text{ m}$. The corresponding normalized mode shapes match Guo and Yang (2011)'s particular solutions.

4. FINAL REMARKS

A Lie symmetry method-based approach has been proposed to compute general solutions for the mode shape equation of non-uniform rods modeled according to the elementary rod theory. An admitted Lie symmetry group provided an order reduction to such mode shape equation, transforming it into a first-order Riccati equation. Finding closed-form solutions for the Riccati equation and recovering them in the space of the mode shape variables provides a systematic procedure for determining general solutions for non-uniform rods. Mode shapes arise from these general solutions by considering the appropriate boundary conditions for rods. In this context, numerous literature works based on ad hoc methods derive from the Lie symmetry method. The systematicity of the Lie symmetry method for solving DEs can lead to extensions for different elastic vibrating structures in future works, e.g., non-uniform beams and plates.

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